

Investigation of effect of Covid -19 on air quality using geospatial technology in Tamil Nadu, India

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Abstract

The state Tamil Nadu is one of the populous state in India and now it is in critical situation because of COVID-19. The first confirmed case was reported in Tamil Nadu on 7th March 2020. Till 1st June 2021, COVID cases has been increased to 2096516 in Tamil Nadu. The government of Tamil Nadu announced the lockdown for entire State and stopped all transports and manufacturing industries due to high increment of COVID cases. However, as a cover step, these steps have a beneficial impact on the atmosphere in terms of mitigating harmful characters, such as temperature, ambient ozone, nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), carbon monoxide (CO), formaldehyde (HCHO) and methane (CH₄). In the present study, the pressure of COVID-19 on various air quality parameters such as temperature, ozone, NO₂, CH₄, SO₂, CO and HCHO were investigated which shows the changes before lockdown and after lockdown using geospatial technology. For this study, web data used to prepare different spatial distribution maps to find the percentage of change in all parameters after lockdown and compared to before lockdown. Based on this study, the method of interpretation was proposed, which is more precise within a certain range of extent and it will provide a propitious information for all Governments and public health officials.

Keywords: Geospatial Analysis; GIS; COVID-19; Tamil Nadu; Air quality parameters

1 Introduction

In December 2019, Wuhan, in China β -corona virus provoked the cluster of pneumonia cases. On 12 January 2020, WHO has notified the first name of corona virus as 2019 novel corona virus (2019-nCoV). Corona virus Study Group (CSG) of the International Committee and WHO officially referred as corona virus disease 2019 (COVID-19) and suggested the new name that it can be called as SARS-CoV-2, both issued on 11 February 2020. On 7 January 2020 the first isolation of SARS-CoV-2 from the patient was made by the great researchers in China within a very short period of time and issued the SARS-CoV-2 genome sequence (Lu et al. 2020). In China, COVID-19 have attained a total cases of 79,968 including 2873 deaths have been reported since 1 March 2020

(WHO, 2020). The results of the study stated that the basic replication number (R₀) of SARS-CoV-2 was approximately 2.2 (Riou et al. 2020) or more (range from 1.4 to 6.5) (Liu et al. 2020) and that the pneumonia clusters (Chan et al. 2020) add to the scientific evidence of a perpetual increase in human-to-human transference of the COVID-19 epidemic. Several studies have used air quality models for measuring air quality which helps in evaluating safety impacts. In certain situations, interpolated amounts of air quality dispersion equations have been found to understate particulate matter (PM) amounts (Mohan et al.2011; Rood, 2014; Kumar et al.2015). Air quality modeling comprises of all emission data from different documented sources of air pollution. Nevertheless, some anonymous origin are missing, particularly those of area sources such as secondary aerosol emission and re-suspended dust. In addition, on-site hourly meteorological data for various parameters are needed for modeling and therefore the measured air quality was used for this analysis. In assessment of air quality the application of GIS is very valuable for mapping and reviewing data on air pollutants. The GIS analysis of air quality and health risk maps aids in deciding the relationship between air quality distribution, population density and population health risks. The geo statistical study of GIS functionalities was used to assess the association of long-term exposure to air pollutants. Worldwide, the second wave of COVID-19 seems possible. The inspection of various meteorological parameters on COVID-19 is essential in forecasting the evolution of this pandemic in upcoming months. In particular, GIS can be essential tools for representing air quality changes in a spatial analysis. For example, GIS technology can be used to create a thematic maps of the various air quality parameters. In this study, the thematic maps of various meteorological parameters will be prepared which may help the researchers and program developers in gaining knowledge about the GIS and spatial analysis studies on COVID-19 in Tamil Nadu. The aim of this research is to show the consequences of COVID – 19 and its impacts on air quality changes before and after lockdown in Tamil Nadu.

2 Materials and Methodology

2.1 Study Area

The state Tamil Nadu, India is located in southern part of India and bounded by Bay of Bengal (east), Kerala (west), Andhra Pradesh (north) and Karnataka (north-west). The state capital is Chennai, which is located at the northeastern. The peoples in this state generally speaks Tamil and is known for its culture and heritage. Generally it has agricultural land, with some industrial developments in major cities such as Chennai with an area of 130,058 km². Based on the 2011 Census of India, the total population is 72,138,958 and population density is shown on map (Fig.1). The climate is tropical, month of May and June have maximum daily temperature (Saravanan et al. 2018). In Chennai the average temperature is 38°C and minimum of low as 20°C. In the month of December and January the temperature usually rise from about 21°C into the mid about 30°C daily. The average annual precipitation ranges from 630 and 1,900 mm and it is falling mainly between October and December during northeast monsoon.

Figure 1: Study area map show district-wise population density in Tamil Nadu, India

2.2 Data Collection

The COVID-19 affected patients of 38 districts in the state of Tamil Nadu was collected from the Department of Health and Family Welfare as per 1 June 2021. The various air quality data was collected from the NASA website (<https://giovanni.gsfc.nasa.gov/>). The spatial analysis was performed using the GIS softwares.

3 Results and Discussions

The emission data of major air pollutants such as temperature, ozone, NO₂, CH₄, SO₂, CO and HCHO were

collected. For spatial analysis of air pollutants the data was collected as average concentration, mean monthly value, emission rate and meteorological data. The meteorological data was wind speed, wind direction, atmospheric stability, mixing height, humidity and rainfall. The inverse distance weighted (IDW) is one of the spatial analysis tool present in ArcGIS and was used to provide a potential health risk map.

3.1 Air quality Index (AQI)

The high AQI value represent the high pollution level and which is a major concern to human health (Chaudhary et al. 2013). If AQI value is above the 100 then it correspond to bad air (unhealthy) and if it is below 100, it means it is in the category of satisfactory. Further, AQI can be of six categories with specific color to each category for better understanding about their toxic level. The major air quality parameter are atmospheric ozone, nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), carbon monoxide (CO), Formaldehyde (HCHO) and methane (CH₄).

3.2 Temperature

Generally the characteristic of the atmosphere temperature is showing unceasing change. The study area shows the change in temperature, before and after lockdown ranges between (2.97k - 2.98k) and (2.96k - 2.98k). The minimum temperature of 2.6k was recorded during April to may 2021 after lockdown and maximum of 2.98k during February to March 2021 before lockdown are depicted graphically in Figures 2a and 2b.

Figure 2: The map (a) Average temperature variation map (before Covid-19 , and (b) Average temperature variation map (after Covid-19 lockdown)

3.3 Ozone

The strong scientific interest in ambient ozone emerged at the beginning of the 1970s in relation to the question of potential supersonic shipping impacts on the ozone layer. Nevertheless, ground level ozone is a toxic air pollutant that impacts both human and the climate. It is triggered by chemical interactions between volatile organic compounds and nitrogen oxides. This is generated when contaminants released by automobiles

and chemical industries. These pollutants will cause a major public health issues like throat discomfort, chest pain, nausea, swelling of the airways, decreased lung capacity, damage to lung tissue, and exacerbate bronchitis, emphysema, and asthma. The result of this research work was that the ozone concentration ranges in the 0 to 5.5 kg/kg lockdown before Covid-19 and the 0 to 5.1 kg/kg geospatial variation map shown in Fig.3a and 3b were reduced after lockdown.

Figure 3: The map of (a) Average ozone concentration map (before Covid-19 lockdown) , (b) Average ozone concentration map (after Covid-19 lockdown)

3.4 Nitrogen dioxide

The NO₂ produce due to the mixture of combustion in particular, road or indoor combustion. Infact, any health risks identified may also have been correlated with certain combustion materials, such as ultrafine particles, nitrous oxide (NO), particulate matter or benzene. Although several studies on both indoor and outdoor, have attempted to focus on the health risks of NO₂. Nitrogen dioxide is discharged through the combustion of fossil fuels and also a highly reactive pollutant. Traffic pollution is the main source of NO₂ and is extremely toxic to the public exposed to long and short-term exposure. The 4.6 million people die worldwide per annum due to the problems associated with NO₂ emissions (Muhammad, et. al., 2020). The continuous exposure of NO₂ lesser than 0.1 ppm in the air to the period of three years. This causes medical issues like bronchitis, emphysema, and affects the performance of lungs (Boningari and Smirniotis, 2016). The effect of Covid-19 the No₂ concentration range is 3.10 to 5.54 1/cm² before lockdown it is reduced in the range of 2.99 to 5.50 1/cm₂ in after lockdown the spatial thematic map shown in Fig.4a and 4b.

3.5 Sulfur dioxide

The level of pollution that can cause harm is determined by air quality standards. The air quality requirements are based on the specific comparison exposure period for each pollutant, such as regular, monthly, hourly, etc. The main source of sulfur dioxide (SO₂) is industrial activity, e.g. thermal power generation, mineral ores, industrial activities that burn fossil fuels, emis-

Figure 4: The map (a) Average nitrogen dioxide concentration map (before Covid-19 lockdown) and (b) Average nitrogen dioxide concentration map (after Covid-19 lockdown)

sions from motor vehicles, etc. (Biersteker, 1976; Chen et al., 2012). Health problems caused by SO₂ include cough, shortness of breath, bronchitis, fatigue, etc. and causes acidic precipitation due to the formation of sulphuric acid. The maximum range of SO₂ concentration 5.374 to 1208 kg m⁻³ and the minimum 8.081 to 1117 kg m⁻³ reduced after Covid-19 lockdown the map shown in Fig.5a and 5b.

Figure 5: The map (a) Average Sulfur dioxide Concentration Map (before Covid-19 lockdown) and (b) Average Sulfur dioxide Concentration Map (after Covid-19 lockdown)

3.6 Carbon monoxide

The key causes of carbon monoxide are cars, water heaters and clothes dryers, etc., which are at high risk where machinery has inadequate ventilation and is placed in a confined space (Atimtay et al., 2000). It is observed that 1/3 of the carbon monoxide related deaths occur while the person is sleeping. After inhalation the CO enters the lungs through the bloodflow, and attached to the hemoglobin and, as a result, oxygen cannot travel through the molecule. If this exposure prolongs then it

has a major probability of affecting the main functioning organs such as heart and brain as it resists and decreases the ability to carry a oxygen in bloodstreams. (Harvard, 2019). The effect of this pandemic virus the change of Co concentration in before and after lockdown ranges decreased in 1.0 to 1.24 ppbv to 0.93 to 1.09 ppbv the spatial variation map shown in Fig.6a and 6b.

Figure 6: The map (a) Average carbon monoxide concentration map (before Covid-19 lockdown), and (b) Average carbon monoxide concentration map (after Covid-19 lockdown)

3.7 Formaldehyde

Formaldehyde is the organic compound occurs naturally in the world. The natural background concentration is $< 1 \text{ g/m}^3$ with a mean of approximately 0.5 g/m^3 (2). The concentrations of outdoor air in Urban environment are more variable and depends on local conditions; the annual average is usually between 1 and 20 g/m^3 . Formaldehyde is formed primarily by various natural and anthropogenic activities. The major release of this compound is due to the combustion of various bush, forest fires and also by the emissions during the volcanic eruptions. Traffic pollutions and many industries producing gases are the main sources of anthropogenic activities. The range of HCHO in this study minimum $< 1 \text{ molecules/cm}^2$ and maximum 1 molecules/cm^2 map shown in Fig.7a and 7b.

3.8 Methane

In Earth, methane mostly presents in the atmosphere (Dlugokencky et al., 2016). The concentration of methane in atmosphere is pretty high because the methane is the very potent green house gases in the earth atmosphere. The study results range of CH_4 is 1.845 to 1.858 ppbv in before lockdown and after lockdown it is 1.834 to 1.858 ppbv map shown in Fig.8a and 8b. The effect of the lockdown on different environmental parameters has been addressed. There is also a large reduction in the amount of emissions in the main economies of the world. In India, the state of Tamil Nadu has a heavy incidence of illness and high mortality owing to air pollution. A significant number of deaths in India as a whole, and in particular in the Tamil Nadu, are due to air

Figure 7: The map (a) Average formaldehyde concentration map (after Covid-19 lockdown) and (b) Average formaldehyde concentration map (before Covid-19 lockdown)

Figure 8: The map (a) Average methane concentration map (before Covid-19 lockdown) and (b) Average methane concentration map (after Covid-19 lockdown)

pollution problems. With the dissemination of COVID-19 in Tamil Nadu, the policy implemented was closed down and all the operations in the country are coming to an end. During this period, several of the metrics indicate rejuvenation. The main effect that can be visualized is the reduction of the air quality parameters as compared to both before lockdown and after lockdown. Since Chennai is one of the most polluted cities in the state, so it is taken as a representative case. From the above geospatial results and analysis, it has been observed that effect of various air quality parameters during lockdown shows a consequent decrease in the associated parameters of pollutants. It can be said that nature is in self-healing mode at this distressing time.

4 Conclusion

This research report states that air emissions and its harmful effects on air quality control for public safety and evaluation of public health. The issue of air emissions from various sources may be addressed through geospatial research. GIS help in creating risk maps of the region. The influence of the lockdown is the collapse of classrooms, universities, markets for commercial institutions, warehouses and public transport. A significant proportion of the planet suffers from air pollution-related diseases. In this distressing moment, however, nature is in self-healing mode, since many of the dangerous toxins in the environment are at minimal rates. The effect on environmental parameters attributable to the lockdown as a preventive measure for COVID-19 was examined in this paper for Tamil Nadu. The lockdown results in the reduction of emission results such as temperature, Ozone (O₃), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), carbon monoxide (CO), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), formaldehyde (HCHO) and methane (CH₄) have been observed across. Nature is rejuvenating at this moment, because there is a large decrease in toxic contaminants that are detrimental to human wellbeing and the climate. This research is of interest to decision leaders, policymakers and scientific practitioners to evaluate and navigate the effect of different variables on the elimination of pollution so that potential facilities and policies can be adjusted accordingly.

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